

Detecting local outliers using the spatially smoothed MRCD estimator

Patricia Puchhammer¹, Peter Filzmoser²

¹*TU Wien - Institute of Statistics and Mathematical Methods in Economics,
Wiedner Hauptstr. 8 , Vienna, Austria*

e-mail: patricia.puchhammer@tuwien.ac.at

²*TU Wien - Institute of Statistics and Mathematical Methods in Economics,
Wiedner Hauptstr. 8 , Vienna, Austria*

e-mail: peter.filzmoser@tuwien.ac.at

Many methods are available for multivariate outlier detection but until now only a hand full are developed for spatial data where there might be observations differing from their neighbors, so-called local outliers. There are methods based on a pairwise Mahalanobis distance approach, however the type of the covariance matrices used is not yet agreed upon and covers only a global covariance (Filzmoser et al. (2013)) and a very local covariance structure (Ernst and Haesbroeck (2016)), more precisely one covariance estimation per observation.

To bridge the gap between the global and local approach by providing a refined covariance structure we develop spatially smoothed robust and regular covariance matrices based on the MRCD estimator (Boudt et al. (2020)) for pre-defined neighborhoods. As well known from the MCD literature, a subset of observations, the so-called H-set, is obtained by optimizing an objective function. In our case we obtain a set of optimal H-sets from minimizing an objective function which is based on a linear spatial smoothing design of local covariance matrices.

A heuristic algorithm based on the notion of a C-step is developed to find the optimal set of H-sets which also shows stable convergence properties in general. We demonstrate the applicability of the new covariance estimators and the importance of a compromise between locality and globality for local outlier detection with simulated and real world data including measurements of Austrian weather stations and further compare the performance with other state-of-the-art methods from statistics and machine learning.

This project has received funding by the European Commission within the Horizon 2021 programme under grant agreement ID 101057741.

References:

- [1] Filzmoser, P., Ruiz-Gazen, A., and Thomas-Agnan, C.: Identification of local multivariate outliers. *Statistical Papers* **55**, (2013), 29–47.
- [2] Ernst, M. and Haesbroeck, G.: Comparison of local outlier detection techniques in spatial multivariate data. *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery* **31** (2016), 371–399.
- [3] Boudt, K., Rousseeuw, P. J., Vanduffel, S., and Verdonck, T.: The minimum regularized covariance determinant estimator. *Statistics and Computing* **30** (2020), 113–128.